

Correlation between prevalence of suicidal ideation and suicidal behaviours among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients

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Suicide is the fourth leading cause of mortality in the world. The majority of it originated from developing countries, notably the Philippines. Substance abuse, particularly illicit drugs, can lead to suicidal thoughts, causing impulsivity, aggression, and burdensomeness. Individuals need supervision and guidance to prevent these thoughts from turning into behavioural acts. The Philippines lacks literature on suicidality incidence and its relationship with suicidal ideations and suicidal behaviours among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients. This study aims to determine the prevalence of suicidal ideations and behaviours among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients using a representative sample of 102 respondents aged 18 to 60 in Bulacan, Philippines. The study used a quantitative approach and a correlational linear regression method. The population was randomised using simple random sampling and the Columbia Suicide Severity Rating Scale was utilised to assess the magnitude and significance of suicidal ideations and suicide behaviours. Results showed that two out of every ten self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients have varied ideations that increase their risk of suicidality. Nearly one in ten engage in suicidal behaviours, contributing to suicide deaths. Although suicidal thoughts contribute to 20.7% of variability in suicidal actions, the connection is not statistically significant (p -value > 0.313). This suggests that suicidal ideation is part of an individual's thought process, not necessarily leading to an attempt. The study will help nursing practice implement a Preventing Addiction-Related Suicide (PARS) programme and suicide risk assessments, focusing on suicidal ideations for self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients.

Keywords: drugs; mental health; Philippines; suicidal ideation; suicide;

The World Health Organization (WHO) has recognised suicide mortality as a significant public health concern, with an alarming annual toll of over 703,000 deaths globally. Suicide stands as the fourth leading cause of mortality among individuals aged 15 to 29, with a striking 77% of these cases occurring in low- or middle-income countries (WHO, 2023). In the Philippines, the gravity of this issue is underscored by data from the National Center for Mental Health, which reported receiving 21,468 calls, of which 7,600 were related to suicide. The majority of these calls came from individuals aged 18 to 30, with an additional 4,800 calls from those under 17 years old (Pinlac, 2023). Furthermore, records from the Department of Health (DOH; 2022) in Central Luzon indicate 68 completed suicide cases, with victims ranging from 15 to 72 years old (Barela, 2023).

Suicide and suicidality are intricately linked concepts that encompass a range of behaviours, including deliberate self-harm, suicidal ideation, planning, and attempts. These behaviours are often driven by complex emotional and psychological factors (De Beurs et al., 2021). Suicidal ideations, which are thoughts of ending one's life, can arise from a variety of stressful or overwhelming situations and may lead to both suicidal attempts and non-suicidal self-injurious behaviour (SIB). Findings from van den Bogaard et al. (2018) emphasises that individuals engaging in SIB may face physiological impairments that could potentially lead to death. Additionally, adherence to psychiatric medications, which may lead to addiction, and cognitive or emotional impairments such as humiliation, hopelessness, and guilt, are critical factors to consider. It is essential to recognise that suicidality is a behavioural issue rather than a psychological illness, necessitating a nuanced approach to intervention and treatment.

The relationship between suicidality and substance use, particularly the use of cannabis, has been well-documented. Substances can exacerbate suicidal behaviour by increasing lethality, reducing anxiety, and impairing judgement, which can lead to impulsivity, disinhibition, and feelings of despair and burdensomeness (Carballo et al., 2020; Estrada et al., 2019). These factors underscore the complexity of addressing suicidality in individuals struggling with substance abuse.

International research has extensively explored the predictors of suicidality, particularly among children and adolescents. Findings suggest that this demographic is more susceptible to suicidal thoughts and behaviours due to a combination of emotional, sociodemographic, and social support factors (Pinto-Coelho & Relojo, 2017). Early suicidal thoughts have been closely linked to subsequent suicide attempts, highlighting the need for early intervention and support. However, despite these insights, there remains a lack of validity and reliability in many studies on suicidal behaviour, particularly in fields such as public health, nursing practice, and neurology (Alvarez-Subiela et al., 2022; Fonseca-Pedrero et al., 2022).

In the context of the Philippines, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding suicidal self-injurious behaviour, both with and without the intent to die. To date, no studies have specifically focused on the incidence of suicidality and the relationship between suicidal ideations and attempts among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients. This study aims to address this gap by examining the prevalence and significance of suicidal ideations and attempts among drug-dependent patients.

The findings of this study can potentially make a substantial contribution to nursing practice by enhancing nurses' understanding of the interplay between suicidal ideation and attempts among self-injurious drug patients. This knowledge will enable nurses to develop more effective intervention strategies and support systems to prevent both suicide and self-harm, ultimately improving the care provided to these vulnerable individuals. By deepening the understanding of these phenomena, this study aims to contribute significantly to the field of mental health, particularly in the areas of suicide prevention and substance abuse treatment.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically utilising a correlational analysis approach to examine the relationship between suicidal ideations and suicidal behaviours among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients. The methodology prioritised objective measurements and statistical analyses to identify patterns and relationships between the variables.

The research was conducted across six drug rehabilitation facilities in Bulacan, Philippines. These facilities cater to individuals aged 18 to 60 undergoing drug addiction recovery, specifically those in the action and maintenance stages of recovery. A total of 102 participants were recruited using purposive sampling to ensure the inclusion of individuals relevant to the study's focus – those actively engaged in their recovery journey. However, a discrepancy of 11 participants was noted during the data collection process, which was addressed to maintain the integrity of the study.

The Columbia Suicide Severity Rating Scale (C-SSRS) was utilised as the primary research instrument to assess the magnitude and significance of suicidal ideations and behaviours. The C-SSRS underwent meticulous translation and validation procedures to ensure its applicability and reliability in the local context. The instrument was administered through face-to-face data collection, allowing for accurate and comprehensive responses from participants.

The data collection process was carefully planned and executed in several stages. Authorisation was obtained from the rehabilitation facilities, and stakeholders were engaged to ensure smooth implementation. Participants were recruited based on the inclusion criteria, and informed consent was obtained to ensure ethical compliance. The research team conducted face-to-face interviews with participants, ensuring clarity and accuracy in responses.

Ethical principles were strictly adhered to throughout the study. Participant well-being was prioritised, and measures were taken to protect their privacy and confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions.

The collected data were subjected to various statistical treatments to uncover relationships and patterns. Frequency and percentage analysis were used to describe the demographic profile of participants and the prevalence of suicidal ideations and behaviours. Linear regression analysis was employed to determine the correlation between suicidal ideations and suicidal behaviours, providing insights into the predictive relationship between the variables.

RESULTS

Table 1 summarises the demographic profile of participants from various drug rehabilitation facilities in Bulacan. Of the 102 respondents, 79.41% were male, and 20.59% were female. The majority (54.90%) were in the early adult age group (18 to 38 years old), followed by 42.16% in the middle adult age group (40 to 59 years old), and 2.94% in the old age group (60 years and above). These findings align with national statistics, which show a higher prevalence of males and younger adults in drug rehabilitation facilities.

The distribution of respondents across rehabilitation facilities shows that the REACH Treatment and Rehabilitation Center, Inc. (REACHTRC) had the highest representation, with 23.53% of participants. Turning Point Rehabilitation Center (TPRH) and JO Reformation Center Clinic (JORC) each contributed 21.57%, while Balay Silangan Drug Reformation Center (BSDRC) accounted for 18.63%. Rebirth Philippines Therapeutic Community Foundation Inc. (RPTCFI) and Bridges of Hope Bulacan

(BOHB) had smaller representations, with 9.80% and 4.90%, respectively. This distribution highlights the varying capacities and approaches to care among the facilities.

Regarding the stages of drug recovery, 37.25% of respondents were in the action stage, while 62.75% were in the maintenance stage. The maintenance stage, which focuses on sustaining positive changes and preventing relapse, is critical in addiction recovery. Respondents in this stage were more likely to provide reliable responses about their suicidal ideations and behaviours.

Table 1
 Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents from different rehabilitation facilities.

Demographics	<i>f</i>	%
Gender		
Male	81	79.41%
Female	21	20.59%
Age		
18-39 (Early Adult)	56	54.90%
40-59 (Middle adult)	43	42.16%
60+ (Old old)	3	2.94%
Facilities		
REACHTRCI	24	23.53%
TPRC	22	21.57%
JORCC	22	21.57%
BSDRC	19	18.63%
RPTCFI	10	9.80%
BOHB	5	4.90%
Stage of drug recovery		
Active stage	38	37.25%
Maintenance Stage	64	62.75%

Table 2 presents the frequency and distribution of various suicidal ideations among the participants. The findings indicate that 30% of respondents reported wishing to be dead, which is often the initial step toward suicidal risk and requires close monitoring. Additionally, 28% of participants experienced non-specific active suicidal thoughts, a moderate level of ideation associated with an 11-fold increased risk of suicide attempts.

A total of 19% of respondents reported active suicidal ideation involving methods but without intent to act, classified as moderately severe, with a 13-fold increased risk of suicide attempts. Sixteen percent experienced active suicidal ideation with some intent to act but without a specific plan, considered severe and associated with a 19-fold increased risk. Lastly, 11% of participants reported active suicidal ideation with both a specific plan and intent to act, classified as very severe, with a 34-fold increased risk of suicide attempts.

Table 2

Frequency and percentage distribution of suicidal ideations among self-injurious drug patients

Indicators	f	%
Participants who have wished to be dead	31	30%
Participants who have not wished to be dead	71	70%
Participants with non-specific active suicidal thoughts	29	28%
Participants who do not have any non-specific active suicidal thoughts	73	72%
Participants with active suicidal ideation via any methods without intent to act	19	19%
Participants who do not have any active suicidal ideation via any methods without intent to act	83	81%
Participants with active suicidal ideation with some intent to act but without a specific plan	16	16%
Participants who do not have any active suicidal ideation with some intent to act but without a specific plan	86	84%
Participants with active suicidal ideation with specific plan and intent	11	11%
Participants who do not have any active suicidal ideation with specific plan and intent	91	89%

Table 3 highlights the frequency and distribution of suicidal behaviours among the study's respondents. The findings show that 17% of participants reported actual suicide attempts, which are the most significant risk factor for fatality related to suicidal acts. However, the majority (83%) did not engage in such attempts, suggesting that substance abuse does not always lead to suicidal behaviours.

Interrupted suicide attempts were reported by 9% of respondents, while 91% did not experience such incidents. Individuals with interrupted attempts are three times more likely to die by suicide, but the data indicates that most participants did not progress to this stage. Aborted suicide attempts were reported by 12% of respondents, while 88% did not engage in such behaviours. These attempts are associated with a higher likelihood of progressing to fatal suicide attempts, but the majority of participants did not exhibit this behaviour.

Preparatory acts of suicidal behaviour, considered the most severe due to their high lethality, were reported by 6% of respondents, while 94% did not engage in such acts. This suggests that substance abuse alone does not consistently lead to suicidal behaviours.

Table 3

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Suicidal Behaviours Among Self-Injurious Drug Patients

Indicators	f	%
Participants who have had actual attempts of suicide	17	17%
Participants who have not had actual attempts of suicide	85	83%
Participants who have had interrupted suicide attempts	9	9%
Participants who have not had any interrupted suicide attempts	93	91%
Participants who have had aborted suicide attempts	12	12%
Participants who have not had aborted suicide attempts	90	88%
Participants who have engaged in preparatory acts of behaviour	6	6%
Participants who have not engaged in preparatory acts of behaviour	96	94%

This study was conducted to determine the significant relationship between suicidal ideations and suicidal behaviours among self-injurious drug patients. A linear regression analysis method was utilised, with a null hypothesis between the study variables. Results, as shown in Table 4, reveal that

suicidal ideations explain 20.7% (adjusted R^2) of the variance in suicidal behaviours, $F(1.78, p < 0.313)$. Specifically, Suicidal Ideations ($\beta = 0.687, t = 1.3357, p < 0.313$) are not significantly correlated with suicidal behaviours. The Q-Q plot in Figure 1 further illustrates the distribution of residuals, confirming the lack of a significant relationship between the two variables.

The R-value of $\beta = 0.687$ further supports the lack of a significant relationship between suicidal ideation and suicidal behaviours. The R^2 value of 0.471 indicates that 47.1% of the variance in suicidal behaviours can be attributed to suicidal ideations, while the adjusted R^2 of 0.207 shows that only 20.7% of the variance is explained by the predictor variable. This suggests that other factors, such as gender, age, economic level, and physical and psychological factors (e.g., smoking, alcohol use, drug use, violence, and depression), may play a more significant role in influencing suicidal behaviours.

Table 4
 Linear Regression Correlation Analysis between Suicidal Ideation and Suicidal Behaviours

Model Fit Measures							
Mode	R	R^2	Adjusted R^2	F	df1	df2	p
1	0.687	0.471	0.207	1.78	1	2	0.313

Model Coefficients – Behaviours %						
Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p	Standard Estimate	
Intercept	0.402	8.205	0.0490	0.965	-	
Ideations %	0.451	0.338	1.3357	0.313	0.687	

Figure 1
 Q-Q Plot between suicidal ideations and suicidal behaviours

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to explore the relationship between suicidal ideations and suicidal behaviours among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients. The findings provide valuable insights into the prevalence and dynamics of suicidality within this population, highlighting the complexity of the relationship between these two phenomena.

The demographic distribution of participants, as shown in Table 1, reflects the diversity of respondents across various rehabilitation facilities in Bulacan. The majority of participants were male (79.41%) and in the early adult age group (54.90%), consistent with national trends in drug rehabilitation admissions (Dangerous Drugs Board, 2022). The representation of participants from different facilities underscores the reach of the study and the diversity of care approaches among rehabilitation centres. This diversity is critical in understanding the broader context of suicidality among self-injurious drug patients.

The prevalence of suicidal ideations, as detailed in Table 2, reveals that 30% of respondents reported wishing to be dead, while 28% experienced non-specific active suicidal thoughts. These findings align with research by Liu and Lee (2023), which emphasises that suicidal ideation, is a critical warning sign requiring close monitoring. The data also show that 19% of participants reported active suicidal ideation involving methods without intent to act, 16% had ideation with some intent but no specific plan, and 11% had ideation with both a specific plan and intent. These levels of ideation, ranging from moderate to very severe, highlight the varying degrees of risk within the population. The findings underscore the importance of early identification and intervention, particularly for individuals with severe ideation, who are 34 times more likely to attempt suicide.

Similarly, the prevalence of suicidal behaviours, as shown in Table 3, indicates that 17% of respondents had made actual suicide attempts, while 9% reported interrupted attempts, 12% reported aborted attempts, and 6% engaged in preparatory acts. These behaviours, particularly preparatory acts, are associated with a significantly higher risk of fatality. However, the majority of respondents did not engage in suicidal behaviours, suggesting that substance abuse does not always lead to such actions. This aligns with findings by Borges and Loera (2010) and Pompili et al. (2010), which highlight the role of specific substances, such as heroin and sedatives, in increasing suicide risk. The data also suggest that impulsivity, psychiatric comorbidities, and other intersecting factors, such as trauma and social inequities, play a significant role in influencing suicidal behaviours (Edalati et al., 2024).

The linear regression analysis, as presented in Table 4 and illustrated in Figure 1, further elucidates the relationship between suicidal ideations and behaviours. The adjusted R^2 value of 0.207 indicates that suicidal ideations explain only 20.7% of the variance in suicidal behaviours, with a p-value of 0.313, confirming the lack of statistical significance. The Q-Q plot in Figure 1 supports this finding, showing a normal distribution of residuals and reinforcing the conclusion that suicidal ideations are not a strong predictor of suicidal behaviours in this population. This finding contrasts with studies by Estrada et al. (2019) and Rizk et al. (2021), which found significant correlations between ideation and behaviour in adolescents. However, the current study suggests that among self-injurious drug patients aged 18 to 60, suicidal ideations are less likely to transition into behaviours, as also noted by Brown et al. (2020).

The lack of a significant relationship between suicidal ideations and behaviours highlights the multifaceted nature of suicidality. Factors such as gender, age, economic level, and physical and

psychological conditions (e.g., smoking, alcohol use, drug use, violence, and depression) may play a more substantial role in influencing suicidal behaviours (Kwon et al., 2022). This complexity underscores the need for tailored interventions that address the unique risks faced by self-injurious drug patients.

In conclusion, while suicidal ideations remain a critical warning sign, they do not necessarily lead to suicidal behaviours. This finding emphasises the importance of addressing the broader factors contributing to suicidality, such as trauma, social inequities, and substance use patterns. Further research is needed to fully understand these dynamics and develop targeted interventions to reduce the risk of suicide in this vulnerable population.

CONCLUSION

This study provides critical insights into the prevalence and dynamics of suicidal ideations and behaviours among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients in Bulacan, Philippines. The findings reveal that while suicidal ideations are relatively common in this population, they do not necessarily translate into suicidal behaviours. This distinction underscores the complexity of suicidality, particularly in the context of substance abuse, where various factors such as impulsivity, trauma, and social inequities interplay.

The lack of a statistically significant relationship between suicidal ideations and behaviours, as evidenced by the adjusted R^2 value of 0.207 and a p-value of 0.313, highlights the need to address other contributing factors beyond ideation. These include demographic, psychological, and environmental influences, which may play a more substantial role in determining suicidal behaviours. The findings also emphasise the importance of tailored interventions that focus on early identification and prevention, particularly for individuals exhibiting severe ideation.

Additionally, the study highlights the critical role of support systems within drug rehabilitation settings. The hierarchical structure observed in these facilities, where senior patients mentor newcomers, reflects the importance of peer support in fostering recovery and mitigating suicidal risk. However, gaps in local government support, particularly in resource allocation and the availability of trained medical professionals remain a significant challenge. Addressing these gaps is essential to improving the quality of care and support for this vulnerable population.

This study underscores the multifaceted nature of suicidality among self-injurious drug rehabilitation clients. It calls for a comprehensive approach to suicide prevention that integrates mental health support, substance abuse treatment, and community-based interventions. By addressing the broader factors influencing suicidality, stakeholders can better support individuals on their journey to recovery and reduce the risk of suicide in this population.

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